

SROC III

Third Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

**November, 2-3rd 2024,
Ethno Complex Vrdnicka kula, Vrdnik**

ADT should be systematically added to pelvis radiotherapy in unfavorable intermediate risk prostate cancer (N0)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13988467

Milana Mitrić Ašković¹

¹*Oncology Institute of Vojvodina*

Prostate cancer (PC) is the second most common cancer and the fifth leading cause of cancer death among men worldwide. According to relevant epidemiological statistics, there were 1.4 million new cases of prostate cancer and 375,000 deaths in 2020. It follows then that today prostate cancer still constitutes a global health problem. In prostate cancer we have three groups of patients: low risk, intermediate risk and high risk. The guidelines are clear for low risk and high risk, on the other hand the recommendations for intermediate risk is not a precise.

The role of androgen deprivation therapy in combination with radiotherapy in intermediate-risk prostate cancer is still controversial, particularly in patients receiving dose-escalated radiotherapy (DERT).

To identify patients with intermediate-risk prostate cancer benefiting from de-escalation of androgen deprivation therapy and/or dose escalated radiation therapy Nabid at all performed a analysis of a phase 3 trial by measuring biochemical failure, distant metastases, prostate cancer-specific mortality, overall survival, and distant metastases-free survival rates according to prognostic intermediate risk factors.

The most studies conclude that in intermediate risk prostate cancer the addition of 6 months of ADT to RT70 or DERT76 significantly improves BF and appears to decrease the risk of death from prostate cancer compared with DERT76 alone with no difference in OS. In the setting of IRPC, ADT plus RT 70 Gy yields effective disease control with a better GI toxicity profile. The negative side for ADT is their late toxicity Nguyen et al shows that receipt of ADT was associated with higher risks of bone fractures, diabetes, dementia, coronary heart disease, acute infarcted myocardium, and sexual dysfunction than in those who did not receive ADT. Roach et al. demonstrated better progression-free survival with pelvis radiotherapy versus prostate-only radiotherapy in patients whose risk of nodal involvement was >15%.

Keywords: Prostate cancer, Radiotherapy, Androgen deprivation therapy

**SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress
2024**

Urednik
Olivera Ivanov

Izdavač
Institut za Onkologiju Vojvodine

Grafička priprema i štampa
NS digiprint, Novi Sad

Tiraž
200

ISBN 978-86-82113-16-4

CIP – Каталогизacija у публикацији
Библиотеке Матице српске, Нови Сад

616-006(048.3)

SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress (3 ; 2024 ; Vrdnik)

Abstract book / Third Serbian Radiation Oncology
Congress, SROC III, November, 2nd-3rd 2024, Ethno Complex
Vrdnicka Kula, Vrdnik ; [urednik Olivera Ivanov]. – Novi
Sad : Institut za onkologiju Vojvodine, 2024 (Novi Sad : NS
digiprint). – 60 str. ; 21 cm

Tiraž 200. – Str. 3: Introduction / Olivera Ivanov.

ISBN 978-86-82113-16-4

a) Онкологија – Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 155485193